
GROWING ISSUES OF ISLAMOPHOBIA IN WESTERN COUNTRIES AND THE ROLE OF THE ISLAMIC WORLD (AN ANALYTICAL STUDY)

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ABSTRACT

The term Islamophobia is used in Europe to intimidate and hate Islam and Muslims. Other religions hated Islam from the beginning. While in today's modern age science has progressed so much and everyone in the world claims to raise the flag of peace but still disgust towards Islam and Muslims is expressed from time to time in the form of various propaganda. Sometimes hate speeches are made against the teachings of Islam and sometimes the Prophet of Islam is ridiculed. Sometimes the Quran is insulted and sometimes Muslims are mistreated. Attempts are made to hurt Muslims in various ways. Muslims are despised. All this is done in the name of freedom of expression. All these activities are carried out on print media and electronic media and such programs are also advertised through these means. An attempt is made to create hatred in the hearts of the people against Muslims. Horrible forms of Islamic teachings are presented. Muslims are portrayed as wild beasts. As a result, the hearts of Muslims are hurt and people of other religions begin to hate Islam as a savage religion and Muslims as oppressors and savages. This article deals with the interpretation of Islamophobia in Europe, the means of promoting Islamophobia, its use and its effects. The true teachings of Islam are misunderstood and propagated. Islam and all Muslims are criticized everywhere by highlighting the mistake of a Muslim. However, all this is tantamount to trying to endanger the peace and order of the world by provoking the Muslims under a well-conceived conspiracy against Islam by looking at the reverse of Islamic teachings.

Keywords: Islamophobia, Anti-Islam Bigotry, Anti-Islam Propaganda, Anti-Islam Sentiment, Anti-Islam Prejudice, Misconceptions of Islam, Islamic Teachings, Peace.

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